

Pre-registration: E073 — Temporal Citation Persistence

Weekly Churn Baseline (Perplexity) · Path B, observational

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Status	Frozen pre-registration — deposited before any data collection
First observation (W1)	Monday 27 July 2026

1. Background and rationale

E073 establishes a weekly churn baseline for citation persistence on Perplexity. Prior GEO Lab work (E027) found zero intra-day variance on proprietary-concept queries, and E016 established a day-scale citation floor. E073 supplements these by measuring persistence at the week scale: whether the set of sources cited for a fixed query set changes meaningfully across weeks. The study is observational (Path B) and runs on a fixed, pre-committed cadence with no interim analysis or extension.

Naming guard. This study concerns persistence and churn, not drift. Drift (spatial / embedding-level change) is the scope of E070 and is not measured here. The two must not be conflated.

2. Hypotheses

H1	Week-scale citation churn is non-trivial, despite the zero intra-day variance observed in E027.
H2	URL-level churn exceeds domain-level churn (sources are less stable at the URL grain than at the domain grain).
H0	Sources are stable across observations (null: no meaningful week-scale churn at either grain).

3. Design and cadence

Fixed cadence: 8 weekly observations. The schedule is fixed in advance. First observation (W1) is Monday 27 July 2026, with one observation per week thereafter for 8 weeks. There is **no extend-if-interesting clause**: the study closes at the 8th observation regardless of results, and no observation will be added, dropped, or rescheduled on the basis of interim findings.

Pre-W1 verification. Before W1, the trio of target pages (/geo-stack/, /extractability/, /retrieval-probability/) will be verified as quiet for the prior week rather than assumed, so the baseline measures natural carousel churn and not GEO Lab interventions (E072 opening-chunk rewrite, E040 surface-form measurement 1–5 Jul, E047 volatility pilot through 2 Jul all settle before W1).

4. Query set

T1 baseline set (E014 / E027 queries, unmodified) plus the three citation-subset URLs: /geo-stack/, /extractability/, and /retrieval-probability/.

5. Measures

Per observation, for each query, capture: the full cited-domain set, the full cited-URL set, binary presence of each tracked URL, and binary presence of thegeolab.net at the domain level. The search_queries fan-out field is captured for context.

Metrics are computed weekly at **both domain and URL grain**: churn-in (new sources relative to the prior week) and retention (prior-week sources still present).

6. Core / carousel threshold

A source is classified **core** if present in at least 6 of the 8 observations ($\geq 75\%$); otherwise it is classified **carousel**. This threshold is fixed in advance.

7. Related identifiers

E016 Day-scale citation floor — supplemented by this week-scale baseline.

E027 Zero intra-day variance on proprietary-concept queries — motivates H1.

External prior SISTRIX AI Citation Drift 2026-05: AI Mode 56% / ChatGPT 74% weekly churn; URL 85% vs domain 74%

This pre-registration is frozen at deposit. Any post-data changes will be recorded only as dated addenda, never inline. The pre-registration block is verbatim and immutable once the Zenodo DOI is minted.